

FutureScape version 1.0

A serious game

About *FutureScape*

Step outside your everyday routine and enter the world of role-playing as statewide decision-makers tackling complex problems in North Carolina’s Coastal Plain. This game leverages role-playing to elicit human behavior in the face of climate change, simulating real-world policy deliberation with imperfect information, limited resources, and pressing time constraints. You'll navigate a scenario based on real data, making decisions under duress and forming coalitions to implement necessary, if imperfect, changes. As you play, embrace the blend of seriousness and playfulness, acknowledging the stakes while remembering it's a game designed to foster creativity and innovative solutions. Enjoy the process, learn from each other, and reflect on the emotional and strategic aspects of decision-making in challenging circumstances.

FutureScape was developed by a team of interdisciplinary experts from North Carolina State University’s Coastal Resilience and Sustainability Initiative and Center for Geospatial Analytics, the North Carolina Museum of Life and Science, and North Carolina Sea Grant. The game was designed to support and debuted during an April 2024 workshop, *Envisioning Transformations in North Carolina’s Coastal Plain*, that brought together experts from academia, state government, and non-governmental partners to collectively envision a just, sustainable, and resilient future for North Carolina’s coastal plain. For questions or assistance with *FutureScape*, contact NC State University’s Coastal Resilience and Sustainability Initiative: coastalresilience@ncsu.edu.

FutureScape data and game board are publicly accessible on Zenodo:
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FutureScape Game Mechanics and Rules

**It is recommended that all players and facilitators read this section prior to playing FutureScape.*

Players:

FutureScape is designed to be played by 4-10 people:

- 3-9 Players
- 1 Facilitator

Players work together collaboratively. The Facilitator acts as the game master: they are a non-player and don't actively contribute to decisions, but instead remind players of rules and keep things moving. Facilitators are provided a script for each turn, and may have information that the players lack. If playing multiple FutureScape games simultaneously, we recommend also having a Lead Facilitator to manage time and events.

Turn Structure:

The game is divided into turns. Each turn represents 10 years of time, and consists of two phases: an Action Phase, where players discuss, deliberate, and invest in Actions to protect land and people, and an Environment Phase, wherein time will pass, the landscape will change, events will occur, and the budget will reset. Each Action Phase lasts 10 minutes. Each Environment Phase occurs directly after each Action Phase and lasts for 5 minutes.

A [Note Taking Template](#) is included in this document for players to take turns documenting the actions invested in during each turn, conflicts or disagreements, changes to assets on the board, and the budget.

**First-time FutureScape players may opt to increase the time for each turn.*

Game Board:

The game board is a map of the Coastal Plain of North Carolina, based on real data. Each hex on the board represents 260 square miles of land east of the Interstate 95 corridor. The colors of the map denote the majority of the land use within that space:

- Forest (green)
- Wetland (brown)
- Agriculture (yellow)
- Developed (gray)
- Water (blue)

Major roads and highways are also included in the map as orange lines. Black circles in the center of some of the hexes indicate population at the start of the game (see [Setup](#), below).

Actions:

Players will have between 3-9 actions available to them every turn. The number of actions available increases throughout the game. Each action has a cost – a number of chips players must spend – associated with it. Each action will affect the game in some way. Some actions allow players to invest in *Site-Specific Interventions* (i.e., investments made on the board) and place these on the board. Players will need to note on the marker what it is that they've placed.

There are three broad types of actions that players may decide to invest in:

- **Resist Actions** invest in resisting changes caused by climate change,
- **Accept Actions** invest in accepting changes and finding alternative solutions, and
- **Direct Actions** invest in directing where, how, and when changes occur.

An [Actions Catalog](#), which contains detailed information and clarifying notes about each action available in *FutureScape*, is included in this document and may be a useful reference resource during the game, especially for facilitators. This document also includes a [Player Cheat Sheet](#), which includes ground rule reminders and brief notes about each available action. Each player should receive a copy of the cheat sheet to keep with them during the game.

Resource Management:

The Bank symbolizes the total budget (capital) that players have for investments. In this game, capital isn't just financial; it also includes political, social, ecological, and other forms of capital. Overspending now may lead to debt, which can have future consequences. Players begin the game with a budget of 10 poker chips, placed in the Bank. Each turn, players will receive a baseline of 10 new poker chips to spend – though this number may increase or decrease based on the assets on the board and with some events that may occur. The chips in the Bank (the budget) are available for players to spend on actions.

During the game, players are managing assets (typically referred to as *asset tokens* throughout this document). These assets are the people and ecology of Coastal North Carolina – and they are closely tied to the budget. Assets included in the game are:

- **Wildlife:** Animals inhabiting forests, fields, and other natural environments.
- **Aquatic Life:** Marine and freshwater organisms in rivers, lakes, wetlands, and oceans.
- **Economic Drivers:** Key industries and activities boosting local economy and jobs.
- **Military Installations:** Bases and facilities that support national defense operations.
- **Population:** Each brick represents a population of 20,000 to 59,000 people. Population is also represented by graduated black circles on the board, intended to assist with the initial setup.
 - Some bricks are red, which denotes that this population is less resilient to climate change.
 - Black bricks are more resilient to climate change.
 - Note that hexes without population are not empty, they just have fewer than 20,000 people.

Ground Rules

Placing assets:

- Each hex on the board has a carrying capacity of three (3) tokens. This means that no more than three asset tokens can be placed in a hex.
 - Stacked *Population* tokens are considered one (1) asset when determining carrying capacity.
 - Roads are counted as one (1) asset when determining carrying capacity. The *Elevate Transportation Infrastructure (R8) Site-Specific Intervention* token is exempt from this limit.
- *Population*:
 - *Population* tokens can only be placed on hexes that contain or border transportation infrastructure.
 - New *Population* tokens cannot be added to a hex that is *Protected*.
 - If a hex is *unDeveloped*, *Population* tokens cannot be stacked (i.e., cannot stack bricks).
 - **Clarifying note:** An *unDeveloped* hex is any hex that is not *Developed* (e.g., *Water, Wetland, Agriculture, or Forest*).
 - If a hex is *Developed*, *Population* tokens can be stacked.
 - If 4 or more *Population* tokens are on a hex, it automatically converts to *Developed*.
 - **Clarifying note:** If an *unDeveloped* hex has three population tokens (i.e., the hex is at carrying capacity) and a fourth is added, the hex converts to *Developed* and *Population* tokens are stacked.
- *Site-Specific Interventions* can be added to any hex, unless otherwise stated on an action card. When adding site-specific interventions to the board, write the ID on the tag.
- *Aquatic Life* tokens can be added to Wetland or Water hexes only.
- *Economic Driver* tokens can be added to any hex.
- *Wildlife* tokens can be added to any non-water hex.
- *Military Installation* tokens can be added to any non-water hex.

Removing assets:

- Some actions or events in the game will involve removing assets from the board. When this happens, move tokens to the *Lost Resources* board area.

Group consensus and conflict resolution:

- Majority consensus is required to invest in an action.
- Majority consensus is required to decide where on the board to place investments.
- The facilitator has the final say.

Game Components and Supplies List

Card decks:

- **Actions:** There are 28 actions in the game divided across three decks: *Resist*, *Accept*, and *Direct*.
 - Resist Action Deck (10 cards), Accept Action Deck (9 cards), Direct Action Deck (9 cards)
 - An [Actions Catalog](#) contains detailed information and clarifying notes for each action
 - A [Player Cheat sheet](#), intended to be handed to each player at the start of the game, lists ground rules and brief details about each action.
 - A [print template for Action cards](#) is included at the end of this document.
- **Weather and Climate Events:** There are 15 different types of climate and weather events that may be drawn. These are listed below, with the recommended numbers of cards to include in the game included in parentheses. A [print template](#) for these cards is included at the end of this document.

Normal (6)	Extreme Heat + Rolling	Category 1 Hurricane (1)
Deep Freeze (1)	Blackouts (1)	Category 2 Hurricane (1)
Wildfire (1)	Non-Hurricane Rain-Induced	Category 3 Hurricane (1)
Harmful Algal Bloom (1)	Flooding Event (1)	Category 4 Hurricane (1)
Drought (2)	Unanticipated Coastal	Category 5 Hurricane (1)
Super Drought (1)	Inundation (3)	Category 6 Hurricane (1)

In addition, four [Hurricane Track Cards](#) are included to use when a hurricane event card is drawn.

Asset tokens:

- Military Installations (, 6)
- Economic Drivers (, 20)
- Population Bricks (, 40 *More Resilient*)
- Bank (, 30)
- Wildlife (, 20)
- Aquatic Life (, 20)
- Site-Specific Interventions (, 13)
- Sticky Notes (8)

Maps:

- Game Board (FutureScapeV1_Game_Board.png; suggested print size: 48 inches wide by 36 inches high; file is available from Zenodo repository linked above).
- Sea level rise projections (i.e., key for 1, 2, and 3 ft of rise), included at the [end of this document](#).

Miscellaneous:

- [Facilitator script](#) (included in this document)
- [Note taking template](#) (optional, included in this document)
- [Post-game debrief](#) discussion prompts (optional, included in this document)
- Stickers (blue, brown, gray, green, yellow)
- Dry erase marker (for *Site-Specific Intervention* tokens)
- Marker(s) (any color)
- Pen(s) (any color)
- Stopwatch or other device to keep time

Setup

Cards and miscellany:

- Set out specific cards from each action deck in their labeled spots beside the board (use the [print template](#) to print these):
 - Hardened Seawall (Resist / Red)
 - Buyout and Move Residents (Accept / Green)
 - Build Living Shoreline (Direct / Blue)
- Set the remaining action cards to the side of the board (keep in their separate decks)
- Weather and Climate Events Decks (use the [print template](#) to print these):
 - Pull out the “Category 6 Hurricane” and set it to the side
 - Shuffle the Weather and Climate Events card deck and set face down beside the facilitator
 - Shuffle the Hurricane Track Cards and set face down beside the facilitator (use the [print template](#) to print these)

Facilitator supplies:

The facilitator should have:

- The [facilitator guide and script](#), and a pen to jot information
- The [sea level rise key](#) and stickers for the *Environment* phase
- [Actions card catalog](#) (optional)
- [Post game debrief](#) discussion prompts (optional)

Player supplies:

Players should have:

- A [player cheat sheet](#) (one per player)
- [Note taking template](#) and pen (optional, shared by all players)

The final setup for the *FutureScape* game is visualized below.

Use the images on subsequent pages to help you set out the following assets:

- Military Bases
- Economic Drivers
- Population Bricks
- Bank
- Wildlife
- Aquatic Life
- Site specific intervention (blank) tokens
- Sticky Notes (optional: keeps track of the decade)

Congratulations! You are now ready to play *FutureScape*!
 Following the instructions in the [Facilitators' Guide and Scripts](#) to begin the game.

Military Installations (6)

- Fort Liberty
- Seymour Johnson Air Force Base
- Cherry Point Marine Corps Air Station
- Piney Island Bombing Range
- Marine Corps Base Camp Lejeune
- Military Ocean Terminal Sunny Point

Aquatic Life (10)

Wildlife (10)

Economic Drivers (10)

Less Resilient Population (25)

More Resilient Population (11)

Black circles on the game board assist with setup:

- one (1) population token is placed in hexes with a small black circle, and
- two (2) stacked population tokens are placed in hexes with a large black circle.

Legend:

- Developed
- Forest
- Agriculture
- Wetland
- Water
- Protected Area
- Aquatic Life
- Economic Driver
- Wildlife
- Less Resilient Population
- More Resilient Population
- Site-specific Intervention
- Military Installation

Population:

- <20k
- 20-59k
- >60k

Year:

250km²
10km

Board-wide Policy

FutureScape

Resist
Accept
Direct

Bank (10)

Legend:

- Developed
- Forest
- Agriculture
- Wetland
- Water
- Protected Area
- Aquatic Life
- Economic Driver
- Wildlife
- Less Resilient Population
- More Resilient Population
- Site-specific Intervention
- Military Installation

Population:

- <20k
- 20-59k
- >60k

Year:

250km²
10km

Board-wide Policy

FutureScape

Resist
Accept
Direct

Site Specific Intervention (10)

Assemble and set to side of board.

Base colors do not matter

- Developed
- Forest
- Agriculture
- Wetland
- Water
- Protected Area
- Aquatic Life
- Economic Driver
- Wildlife
- Less Resilient Population
- More Resilient Population
- Site-specific Intervention
- Military Installation
- Population
 - <20k
 - 20-59k
 - >60k
- Year

Board-wide Policy

FutureScape

Resist
Accept
Direct

Year Sticky Notes

One Stack (2030 labeled on the top)

- Developed
- Forest
- Agriculture
- Wetland
- Water
- Protected Area
- Aquatic Life
- Economic Driver
- Wildlife
- Less Resilient Population
- More Resilient Population
- Site-specific Intervention
- Military Installation
- Population
 - <20k
 - 20-59k
 - >60k
- Year

Board-wide Policy

FutureScape

Resist
Accept
Direct

Facilitators' Guide and Scripts

FutureScape was originally designed to be played as multiple simultaneous games in the same room. Each game has their own Table Facilitator that controls events for the game. A Lead Facilitator is in charge of the room and manages time and full-room events. We recommend playing *FutureScape* with at least two simultaneous games. If you are playing only one game, or playing in a small room, a Table Facilitator can also take on the role of Lead Facilitator.

The *FutureScape* table facilitator is the game master. This guide contains scripts and instructions for *FutureScape* table facilitators. Note that some things are intentionally vague, so as to give table facilitators room to control the game as they see fit.

Key:

Instructions are in regular, un-highlighted text.

Outlined in solid aqua are things Table Facilitators should read aloud.

Outlined in dotted orange are things the Lead Facilitator should read aloud.

Pre-Game Lead Facilitator Script:

What you're about to participate in is a bit out of the ordinary for a professional or academic setting. Consider this your invitation to step outside of your everyday life and expertise and into the world of role-playing. In the experience you're about to go through, you'll roleplay as a team of statewide decision-makers, working together to try to solve sticky and interconnected problems in North Carolina's Coastal Plain.

Why role-playing? It turns out, role-playing is an excellent tool to predict one of the hardest things to account for when it comes to the future under climate change: human behavior. Role-playing, especially in serious games like the one you'll be playing today, can simulate how people might actually have conversations, debate, and make decisions in the future.

The scenario you're going to be working with is based on real data and modeling. Keep in mind that in order to be playable, there's a balance between the scientific and technical accuracy we can represent on a game board and the experience that you all will have as players – or rather – as decision-makers.

Ultimately, this is a more accurate view of how policy is really deliberated over and how decisions are made: with imperfect information, often with too few resources, and with too little time. In the spirit of that, the scenario you'll be role-playing in has the same: you won't have all of the access to the information you might want or need to make decisions, you certainly will not have enough resources to do everything you might want, and you will absolutely not have enough time.

The key here is to explore how decision-making works under real duress and pressure (like real decision-making!), and with less than perfect information. Where are you willing to compromise? What are you willing to let go? Keep that in mind as you're playing: the limitations you're working under are **deliberate**.

There are many of you that will need to be convinced of action. Usually, the easiest action to take in scenarios where the outcomes are uncertain and the tradeoffs are unclear is *inaction*. You'll find that the stakes here are likely too high for inaction. Where are you willing to create coalitions to implement changes even if they are imperfect? How will you work quickly to ensure that the North Carolinians you serve are not victims to a governing body that cannot act?

Ultimately, we're interested in a few things here: obviously, we're interested in you having a good time, having a laugh or two at your own expense, and learning with and from one another. We're also interested in the unique flavors of discomfort, anxiety, and frustration that come with the responsibility for making decisions when you have less time, money, and information that you want. As you play, take stock of your own emotional state and remind yourself: it's just a game.

We're also interested in your learning and your teams' decision making. When you find yourself with a game-relevant question, ask it! The experience is designed also to better understand what further inquiry about the future from multiple disciplines is still needed or requires further exploration. It's a bit meta, but outside of the game, it's possible that these questions might inform real research about the future.

Even as you're in the game, consider why and how you and your team are able to make decisions under somewhat remarkable circumstances: you all may be strangers to one another; you all are learning a complex and overwhelming scenario all together, and you're (hopefully) still somehow able to decide on policies, actions, and decisions that you reasonably believe might be helpful in real life, and in the game.

Most of all, the experience works best – okay, only works – if you as a person can get into the role-playing aspect of it. We tend not to be very good at the concept of play as adults. This is your explicit invitation to play as the most important principle and rule for the following activity. The work that you do is serious and heavy, but the way we interact with one another about it need not always be. Finding innovative solutions to the future demands that we make some space for imagination, creativity, and yes, playfulness. Take as your mandate the overall axioms for serious gaming: have fun, but not too much fun; take it seriously, but not too seriously. Remember – it's a game. But also remember, games are work too.

Table Facilitator “Game on” Script:

You are a team of statewide decision-makers charged with protecting the land and people of the Coastal Plain of North Carolina. First, let’s note our map. Each hex represents 260 square miles of land east of the Interstate 95 corridor. The colors of the map denote the majority of the land use within that space, let’s take a look at the map’s key in the top left hand corner!

- Can someone point to a *Forest* hex?
- How about an *Agriculture* hex? A *Wetland* hex? A *Developed* hex?
- Can someone find a *road*?

Excellent! Now let’s explore the assets on your board. These assets are the people and ecology of coastal North Carolina, and they are closely tied to your budget.

- First, can someone find some *Wildlife* on the board?
- Can someone find some *Aquatic Life*? An *Economic Driver*? A *Military Installation*?

How about *Population*? Good! Note that hexes without population bricks are not empty, they just have fewer than 20,000 people. Each brick represents about 20,000 people. Some bricks are red, which denotes that this population is *Less Resilient* to climate change. Black bricks are *More Resilient* to climate change.

The amount and location of your assets will affect your budget throughout the game. Speaking of which, can someone find the bank for me?

You and your team begin the game with a budget of 10 poker chips. Each turn, you will receive a baseline of 10 new poker chips to spend – though this number may increase or decrease based on the assets on the board and with some events that may occur. Your chips are available for you to spend on your actions.

Let’s look at actions! You will have between 3-9 actions available to you every turn. Each action has a cost – a number of chips you must spend – associated with it. Each action will affect the game in some way.

Some actions allow you to invest in *Site-Specific Interventions* like new infrastructure projects or upgrades. These are represented by these currently blank tokens. When making an investment in a *Site-Specific Intervention*, you will need to note on the token what it is that you’ve placed.

A few other ground rules:

1. No more than three (3) assets can be placed on a hex. Stacked *Population* tokens count as one (1) asset. Roads, including existing roads on the map, are counted as one (1) asset.
 2. *Population* tokens can only be placed on hexes that contain or border transportation infrastructure.
 3. New *Population* tokens cannot be added to a hex that is *Protected*.
 4. If a hex is **unDeveloped**, *Population* tokens **cannot** be stacked. If a hex is **Developed**, *Population* tokens **can** be stacked.
 5. *Economic Driver* tokens can be added to any hex, while *Wildlife* tokens can be added to any non-water hex. *Aquatic Life* tokens can be added to *Wetland* or *Water* hexes only.
1. Majority consensus (____ out of ____) is required **both** to invest in an action **and** to decide where on the board to place investments.
 2. The facilitator (me) has the final say.

Each turn in the game represents 10 years of time, and consists of two phases: an **Action Phase**, where you and your team may discuss, deliberate, and invest in actions, and an **Environment Phase**, wherein time will pass, the landscape will change, events will occur, and your budget will reset.

Your Action Phases will each last 10 minutes. The Environment Phase will occur directly afterwards, and will last for 5 minutes.

Turn 1: Action Phase

The year is **2030**. Your budget is **10** poker chips.

Point to the Bank where 10 poker chips have been added as part of the game setup.

You and your team of statewide decision-makers must act quickly to protect the coastal plain of North Carolina and the people who live there. This turn, you may consider three different policy options available to you for investment.

- There is 1 card available for play from the Resist Action Deck.
- There is 1 card available for play from the Accept Action Deck.
- There is 1 card available for play from the Direct Action Deck.

Each investment has a cost associated with it, which is marked on the card. You may invest in any of these actions as you choose, and you may invest in the same option more than once. Remember that to **invest in an action and to place an investment on the board**, your team must vote and have a majority in favor.

Read each action carefully, as they have different effects and consequences for the people and ecosystems on the coastline.

You may choose to spend none of your poker chips and save them. It is likely, but not guaranteed, that you will have saved poker chips carry over for the next turn.

You and your team have 10 minutes to make decisions about what actions are best for the coastal plain – starting now.

Begin the 10 minute timer for the Actions Phase.

Turn 1: Environment Phase

You and your team have made decisions about the future of the North Carolina Coastal Plain. Let's now explore how these play out over the next 10 years, from 2030-2040.

First, we will choose one (1) climate and weather event card.

- Take one (1) event card from the Climate and Weather Event Card Deck.
- Resolve that event as described on the card. Keep note of Actions that players invested in that may protect hexes.
- *If you drew a hurricane, refer to the hurricane paths maps to select one at random.*

The population of North Carolina's coastal plain is growing! Let's add population to the map.

- You may decide where to add **two (2) Less Resilient Population** tokens to the map.
- If they are placed on hexes with no *Population* tokens, place a gray sticker on the hex to convert it to *Developed*. (Note this is a unique addition during the Environment Phase).

North Carolina's environment is changing!

- Look at the attached map of Sea Level Rise. Select **5 hexes** from the **1 FT** of sea level rise and convert them to *Water* by placing a blue sticker in their center.
- Any *Population* tokens in a hex converted to *Water* must be moved to the *Lost Resources* area.

Return actions cards back into their appropriate decks (*unless* they are still in play, e.g., a "Board-wide Policy"). Shuffle, or instruct players to shuffle, the Resist, Accept, and Direct card decks and place them to the side of the board.

Lastly, we will see how your assets and economy are doing.

1. Give players **10** new poker chips (🎰). They may keep any saved poker chips from the previous turn for their economy.
2. Count how many Economic Drivers (🌿) are on the map: _____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Economic Drivers on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Economic Drivers on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
3. Count how many Wildlife (🦋) are on the map: _____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Wildlife on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Wildlife on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
4. Count how many Aquatic Life (🐟) are on the map: _____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Aquatic Life on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Aquatic Life on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
5. Finally, resolve any Actions that may add or remove chips from the economy:
 - a. Some cards require persistent investment over each turn to keep them on the map. Let players choose whether they'd like to keep them or not.
 - b. Some cards add poker chips to the economy. Add these immediately.

Write the budget at the end of the Environment Phase, keeping track of debt: _____

Turn 2: Action Phase

Remove the top sticky note at the bottom of the board to reveal the year.

The year is **2040**. The Coastal Plain of North Carolina looks like this now. Our state has grown in population, and the coastline has shifted. The actions that you have invested in have benefited North Carolinians and the ecosystems they rely on.

It is up to you to continue to invest in actions that will benefit our Coastal Plain.

Your budget now is _____

You and your team of statewide decision-makers must act quickly to protect the coastal plain of North Carolina and the people who live there. This turn, you may consider **six** different policy options available to you for investment.

- Turn over 2 cards available for play from the Resist Action Deck.
- Turn over 2 cards available for play from the Accept Action Deck.
- Turn over 2 cards available for play from the Direct Action Deck.

Each investment has a cost associated with it, which is marked on the card. You may invest in any of these actions as you choose, and you may invest in the same option more than once. Remember that to **invest in an action and to place an investment on the board**, your team must vote and have a majority in favor.

Read each action carefully, as they have different effects and consequences for the people and ecosystems on the coastline.

You may choose to spend none of your poker chips and save them. It is likely, but not guaranteed, that you will have saved poker chips carry over for the next turn.

You and your team have 10 minutes to make decisions about what actions are best for the coastal plain – starting now.

Begin the 10 minute timer for the Actions Phase.

Turn 2: Environment Phase

There has been a stochastic shock! Let's pay attention to the lead facilitator to learn more.

A Global Conflict has broken out

- Facilitators: Take away all savings.
- Facilitators: Give your players six (6) *Population* tokens to add to their boards. Three (3) must be placed on or adjacent to hexes with a *Military Installation*.
- Facilitators: Give your players six (6) *Economic Driver* tokens to add to their board. They must be placed in hexes containing or adjacent to Military Installations.

Resolve consequences of the stochastic shock immediately, then continue the remainder of the Environment Phase as per usual.

First, we will choose two (2) climate and weather event cards.

- Draw one (1) card from the Climate and Weather Event deck.
- Resolve the event as described on the card. Keep note of Actions that players invested in that may protect hexes.
- **Shuffle the card back into the deck and draw a new card.**
- Repeat this until you have drawn and resolved two (2) climate and weather events.
- *If you drew a hurricane, refer to the hurricane paths maps to select one at random.*

The population of North Carolina's coastal plain is growing! Let's add population to the map.

- You may decide where to add **two (2) Less Resilient Population** tokens to the map.
- If they are placed on hexes with no *Population* tokens, place a gray sticker on the hex to convert it to *Developed*.

North Carolina's environment is changing!

- Look at the attached map of Sea Level Rise. Select **5 hexes** from the **1 FT or 2 FT** of sea level rise and convert them to water by placing a sticker in their center.
- Any *Population* tokens in a hex converted to *Water* must be moved to the *Lost Resources* area.

Our climate is changing!

- Remove the *Deep Freeze* card from the Climate and Weather Event Deck.
- Remove one (1) *Normal* card from the Climate and Weather Event Deck
- Shuffle the Climate and Weather Event Deck.

Return actions cards back into their appropriate decks (*unless* they are still in play, e.g., a "Board-wide Policy"). Shuffle, or instruct players to shuffle, the Resist, Accept, and Direct card decks and place them to the side of the board.

(Turn 2 Environment Phase continues onto next page)

Lastly, we will see how your assets and economy are doing.

1. Give players **10** new poker chips (🎰).
2. Count how many Economic Drivers (🌿) are on the map: _____
 - If there are more than 10 Economic Drivers on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - If there are fewer than 5 Economic Drivers on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
3. Count how many Wildlife (🐦) are on the map: _____
 - If there are more than 10 Wildlife on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - If there are fewer than 5 Wildlife on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
4. Count how many Aquatic Life (🐟) are on the map: _____
 - If there are more than 10 Aquatic Life on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - If there are fewer than 5 Aquatic Life on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
5. Finally, resolve any Actions that may add or remove chips from the economy:
 - Some cards require persistent investment over each turn to keep them on the map. Let players choose whether they'd like to keep them or not.
 - Some cards add poker chips to the economy. Add these immediately.

Write the budget at the end of the Environment Phase, keeping track of debt: _____

Turn 3: Action Phase

Remove the top sticky note at the bottom of the board to reveal the year.

The year is **2050**. The Coastal Plain of North Carolina looks like this now. Our state has grown in population, and the coastline has shifted. The actions that you have invested in have benefited North Carolinians and the ecosystems they rely on.

It is up to you to continue to invest in actions that will benefit our Coastal Plain.

Your budget now is _____

You and your team of statewide decision-makers must act quickly to protect the coastal plain of North Carolina and the people who live there. This turn, you may consider **six** different policy options available to you for investment.

- Turn over 2 cards available for play from the Resist Action Deck.
- Turn over 2 cards available for play from the Accept Action Deck.
- Turn over 2 cards available for play from the Direct Action Deck.

Each investment has a cost associated with it, which is marked on the card. You may invest in any of these actions as you choose, and you may invest in the same option more than once. Remember that to **invest in an action and to place an investment on the board**, your team must vote and have a majority in favor.

Read each action carefully, as they have different effects and consequences for the people and ecosystems on the coastline.

You may choose to spend none of your poker chips and save them. It is likely, but not guaranteed, that you will have saved poker chips carry over for the next turn.

You and your team have 10 minutes to make decisions about what actions are best for the coastal plain – starting now.

Begin the 10 minute timer for the Actions Phase.

Turn 3: Environment Phase

Let's see what happens between 2050 and 2060!

The road systems in North Carolina are deteriorating with more extreme heat and more flooding events. **Do you want to spend 2 chips to upkeep the road systems?** If not, your facilitator (me) will remove 4 hexes with roads on them.

Resolve this immediately. If removing roads, use a marker to cross them out on the board.

Next, we will choose two (2) climate and weather event cards.

- Draw one (1) card from the Climate and Weather Event deck.
- Resolve the event as described on the card. Keep note of Actions that players invested in that may protect hexes.
- **Shuffle the card back into the deck and then draw a new card.**
- Repeat this until you have drawn and resolved two (2) climate and weather events.
- *If you drew a hurricane, refer to the hurricane paths maps to select one at random.*

The population of North Carolina's coastal plain is growing! Let's add population to the map.

- You may decide where to add **three (3) Less Resilient Population** tokens to the map.
- If they are placed on hexes with no *Population* tokens, place a gray sticker on the hex to convert it to *Developed*.

North Carolina's environment is changing!

- Look at the attached map of Sea Level Rise. Select **5 hexes** from the **1 FT or 2 FT** of sea level rise and convert them to water by placing a sticker in their center.
- Any *Population* tokens in a hex converted to *Water* must be moved to the *Lost Resources* area.

Our climate is changing!

- Remove one (1) *Normal* card from the Climate and Weather Event Deck
- Shuffle the Climate and Weather Event Deck.

Return actions cards back into their appropriate decks (*unless* they are still in play, e.g., a "Board-wide Policy"). Shuffle, or instruct players to shuffle, the Resist, Accept, and Direct card decks and place them to the side of the board.

(Turn 3 Environment Phase continues onto next page)

Lastly, we will see how your assets and economy are doing.

1. Give players **10** new poker chips (🎰). They may keep any saved poker chips from the previous turn for their economy.
2. Count how many Economic Drivers (🌿) are on the map: ____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Economic Drivers on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Economic Drivers on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
3. Count how many Wildlife (🐦) are on the map: ____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Wildlife on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Wildlife on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
4. Count how many Aquatic Life (🐟) are on the map: ____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Aquatic Life on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Aquatic Life on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
5. Finally, resolve any Actions that may add or remove chips from the economy:
 - a. Some cards require persistent investment over each turn to keep them on the map. Let players choose whether they'd like to keep them or not.
 - b. Some cards add poker chips to the economy. Add these immediately.

Write the budget at the end of the Environment Phase, keeping track of debt: _____

Read the section below only if your table has accrued debt:

Your legislature raises taxes to pay for accrued debts. This has the positive outcome of clearing your debt, but has the negative effect of angering your tax base, which costs you political capital. The investment cost of each action in the next phase is increased by ____ poker chips.

If players have accrued debt (i.e., if the budget is negative), actions in the next phase will cost more.

- If the budget is between 0 and -5, the cost of each action this turn is increased by **1** poker chip.
- If the budget is between -6 and -10, the cost of each action this turn is increased by **2** poker chips.
- If the budget is -11 or lower, the cost of each action this turn is increased by **3** poker chips.

All debt is now cleared. Write the new budget: _____

Turn 4: Action Phase

Remove the top sticky note at the bottom of the board to reveal the year.

The year is **2060**. The Coastal Plain of North Carolina looks like this now. Our state has grown in population, and the coastline has shifted. The actions that you have invested in have benefited North Carolinians and the ecosystems they rely on.

It is up to you to continue to invest in actions that will benefit our Coastal Plain.

Your budget now is _____

You and your team of statewide decision-makers must act quickly to protect the coastal plain of North Carolina and the people who live there. This turn, you may consider **six** different policy options available to you for investment.

- Turn over 2 cards available for play from the Resist Action Deck.
- Turn over 2 cards available for play from the Accept Action Deck.
- Turn over 2 cards available for play from the Direct Action Deck.

Each investment has a cost associated with it, which is marked on the card. You may invest in any of these actions as you choose, and you may invest in the same option more than once. Remember that to **invest in an action and to place an investment on the board**, your team must vote and have a majority in favor.

Read each action carefully, as they have different effects and consequences for the people and ecosystems on the coastline.

You may choose to spend none of your poker chips and save them. It is likely, but not guaranteed, that you will have saved poker chips carry over for the next turn.

You and your team have 10 minutes to make decisions about what actions are best for the coastal plain – starting now.

Begin the 10 minute timer for the Actions Phase.

Turn 4: Environment Phase

There has been a stochastic shock! Let's pay attention to the lead facilitator to learn more.

There has been a Market Collapse

- Facilitators: Take away half of all savings.
- Facilitators: Remove four *Economic Driver* tokens from the board.
- On your next turn, instead of adding 10 poker chips to your economy, you will add 5.

Resolve consequences of the stochastic shock immediately, then continue the remainder of the Environment Phase as per usual.

The road systems in North Carolina are deteriorating with more extreme heat and more flooding events. **Do you want to spend 2 chips to upkeep the road systems?** If not, your facilitator (me) will remove 4 hexes with roads on them.

Resolve this immediately. If removing roads, use a marker to cross them out on the board.

Next, we will choose two (2) climate and weather event cards.

- Draw one (1) card from the Climate and Weather Event deck.
- Resolve the event as described on the card. Keep note of Actions that players invested in that may protect hexes.
- **Shuffle the card back into the deck and then draw a new card.**
- Repeat this until you have drawn and resolved two (2) climate and weather events.
- *If you drew a hurricane, refer to the hurricane paths maps to select one at random.*

The population of North Carolina's coastal plain is growing! Let's add population to the map.

- You may decide where to add **three (3) Less Resilient Population** tokens to the map.
- If they are placed on hexes with no *Population* tokens, place a gray sticker on the hex to convert it to *Developed*.

North Carolina's environment is changing!

- Look at the attached map of Sea Level Rise. Select **5 hexes** from the **1 FT or 2 FT** of sea level rise and convert them to water by placing a sticker in their center.
- Any *Population* tokens in a hex converted to *Water* must be moved elsewhere on the board.

Our climate is changing!

- Add one (1) Category 6 Hurricane to the Climate and Weather Event Deck.

Return actions cards back into their appropriate decks (*unless* they are still in play, e.g., a "Board-wide Policy"). Shuffle, or instruct players to shuffle, the Resist, Accept, and Direct card decks and place them to the side of the board.

(Turn 4 Environment Phase continues onto next page)

Next, we will see how your assets and economy are doing.

1. Give players **5** new poker chips (🎰). They may keep any saved poker chips from the previous turn for their economy.
2. Count how many Economic Drivers (🌿) are on the map: _____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Economic Drivers on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Economic Drivers on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
3. Count how many Wildlife (🐦) are on the map: _____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Wildlife on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Wildlife on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
4. Count how many Aquatic Life (🐟) are on the map: _____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Aquatic Life on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Aquatic Life on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
5. Finally, resolve any Actions that may add or remove chips from the economy:
 - a. Some cards require persistent investment over each turn to keep them on the map. Let players choose whether they'd like to keep them or not.
 - b. Some cards add poker chips to the economy. Add these immediately.

Write the budget at the end of the Environment Phase, keeping track of debt: _____

Turn 5: Action Phase

Remove the top sticky note at the bottom of the board to reveal the year.

The year is **2070**. The Coastal Plain of North Carolina looks like this now. Our state has grown in population, and the coastline has shifted. The actions that you have invested in have benefited North Carolinians and the ecosystems they rely on.

It is up to you to continue to invest in actions that will benefit our Coastal Plain.

Your budget now is _____

Decide how many actions your players will have to choose from this turn: six (2 actions from each deck) or nine (3 actions from each deck). Fill in the blanks below based on your decision.

You and your team of statewide decision-makers must act quickly to protect the coastal plain of North Carolina and the people who live there. This turn, you may consider ___ different policy options available to you for investment.

- Turn over ___ cards available for play from the Resist Action Deck.
- Turn over ___ cards available for play from the Accept Action Deck.
- Turn over ___ cards available for play from the Direct Action Deck.

Each investment has a cost associated with it, which is marked on the card. You may invest in any of these actions as you choose, and you may invest in the same option more than once. Remember that to **invest in an action and to place an investment on the board**, your team must vote and have a majority in favor.

Read each action carefully, as they have different effects and consequences for the people and ecosystems on the coastline.

You may choose to spend none of your poker chips and save them. It is likely, but not guaranteed, that you will have saved poker chips carry over for the next turn.

You and your team have 10 minutes to make decisions about what actions are best for the coastal plain – starting now.

Begin the 10 minute timer for the Actions Phase.

Turn 5: Environment Phase

Let's see what happens between 2070 and 2080!

The road systems in North Carolina are deteriorating with more extreme heat and more flooding events. **Do you want to spend 2 chips to upkeep the road systems?** If not, your facilitator (me) will remove 4 hexes with roads on them.

Resolve this immediately. If removing roads, use a marker to cross them out on the board.

Next, we will choose three (3) climate and weather event cards.

- Draw one (1) card from the Climate and Weather Event deck.
- Resolve the event as described on the card. Keep note of Actions that players invested in that may protect hexes.
- **Shuffle the card back into the deck and then draw a new card.**
- Repeat this until you have drawn and resolved three (3) climate and weather events.
- *If you drew a hurricane, refer to the hurricane paths maps to select one at random.*

The population of North Carolina's coastal plain is growing! Let's add population to the map.

- You may decide where to add **four (4) Less Resilient Population** tokens to the map.
- If they are placed on hexes with no *Population* tokens, place a gray sticker on the hex to convert it to *Developed*.

North Carolina's environment is changing!

- Look at the attached map of Sea Level Rise. Select **5 hexes** from the **1 FT, 2 FT, or 3 FT** of sea level rise and convert them to water by placing a sticker in their center.
- Any *Population* tokens in a hex converted to *Water* must be moved elsewhere on the board.

Our climate is changing!

- Remove one (1) *Normal* card from the Climate and Weather Event Deck
- Shuffle the Climate and Weather Event Deck.

Return actions cards back into their appropriate decks (*unless* they are still in play, e.g., a "Board-wide Policy"). Shuffle, or instruct players to shuffle, the Resist, Accept, and Direct card decks and place them to the side of the board.

(Turn 5 Environment Phase continues onto next page)

Next, we will see how your assets and economy are doing.

1. Give players **10** new poker chips (🎰). They may keep any saved poker chips from the previous turn for their economy.
2. Count how many Economic Drivers (🌿) are on the map: ____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Economic Drivers on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Economic Drivers on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
3. Count how many Wildlife (🦋) are on the map: ____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Wildlife on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Wildlife on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
4. Count how many Aquatic Life (🐟) are on the map: ____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Aquatic Life on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Aquatic Life on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
5. Finally, resolve any Actions that may add or remove chips from the economy:
 - a. Some cards require persistent investment over each turn to keep them on the map. Let players choose whether they'd like to keep them or not.
 - b. Some cards add poker chips to the economy. Add these immediately.

Write the budget at the end of the Environment Phase, keeping track of debt: _____

Read the section below only if your table has accrued debt:

Your legislature raises taxes to pay for accrued debts. This has the positive outcome of clearing your debt, but has the negative effect of angering your tax base, which costs you political capital. The investment cost of each action in the next phase is increased by ____ poker chips.

If players have accrued debt (i.e., if the budget is negative), actions in the next phase will cost more.

- If the budget is between 0 and -5, the cost of each action this turn is increased by **1** poker chip.
- If the budget is between -6 and -10, the cost of each action this turn is increased by **2** poker chips.
- If the budget is -11 or lower, the cost of each action this turn is increased by **3** poker chips.
- All debt is now cleared. Write the new budget: _____

Turn 6: Action Phase

Remove the top sticky note at the bottom of the board to reveal the year.

The year is **2080**. The Coastal Plain of North Carolina looks like this now. Our state has grown in population, and the coastline has shifted. The actions that you have invested in have benefited North Carolinians and the ecosystems they rely on.

It is up to you to continue to invest in actions that will benefit our Coastal Plain.

Your budget now is _____

Decide how many actions your players will have to choose from this turn: six (2 actions from each deck) or nine (3 actions from each deck). Fill in the blanks below based on your decision.

You and your team of statewide decision-makers must act quickly to protect the coastal plain of North Carolina and the people who live there. This turn, you may consider ___ different policy options available to you for investment.

- Turn over ___ cards available for play from the Resist Action Deck.
- Turn over ___ cards available for play from the Accept Action Deck.
- Turn over ___ cards available for play from the Direct Action Deck.

Each investment has a cost associated with it, which is marked on the card. You may invest in any of these actions as you choose, and you may invest in the same option more than once. Remember that to **invest in an action and to place an investment on the board**, your team must vote and have a majority in favor.

Read each action carefully, as they have different effects and consequences for the people and ecosystems on the coastline.

You may choose to spend none of your poker chips and save them. It is likely, but not guaranteed, that you will have saved poker chips carry over for the next turn.

You and your team have 10 minutes to make decisions about what actions are best for the coastal plain – starting now.

Begin the 10 minute timer for the Actions Phase.

Turn 6: Environment Phase

There has been a stochastic shock! Let's pay attention to the lead facilitator to learn more.

A new Federal Land Protection Act has passed!

- Each facilitator picks 3 *unDeveloped* hexes that are adjacent to or near protected hexes and converts them to protected (draw hashes through the newly protected hexes). Any population tokens on the newly protected hexes are moved to an unprotected hex.
- Add 3 *Wildlife* () to *Water* or *Wetlands* hexes.

Resolve consequences of the stochastic shock immediately, then continue the remainder of the Environment Phase as per usual.

The road systems in North Carolina are deteriorating with more extreme heat and more flooding events. **Do you want to spend 2 chips to upkeep the road systems?** If not, your facilitator (me) will remove 4 hexes with roads on them.

Resolve this immediately. If removing roads, use a marker to cross them out on the board.

Next, we will choose three (3) climate and weather event cards.

- Draw one (1) card from the Climate and Weather Event deck.
- Resolve the event as described on the card. Keep note of Actions that players invested in that may protect hexes.
- **Shuffle the card back into the deck and then draw a new card.**
- Repeat this until you have drawn and resolved three (3) climate and weather events.
- *If you drew a hurricane, refer to the hurricane paths maps to select one at random.*

The population of North Carolina's coastal plain is growing! Let's add population to the map.

- You may decide where to add **three (3) Less Resilient Population** tokens to the map.
- If they are placed on hexes with no *Population* tokens, place a gray sticker on the hex to convert it to *Developed*.

North Carolina's environment is changing!

- Look at the attached map of Sea Level Rise. Select **5 hexes** from the **1 FT, 2 FT, or 3 FT** of sea level rise and convert them to water by placing a sticker in their center.
- Any *Population* tokens in a hex converted to *Water* must be moved elsewhere on the board.

Our climate is changing!

- Remove one (1) *Normal* card from the Climate and Weather Event Deck
- Shuffle the Climate and Weather Event Deck.

Return actions cards back into their appropriate decks (*unless* they are still in play, e.g., a "Board-wide Policy"). Shuffle, or instruct players to shuffle, the Resist, Accept, and Direct card decks and place them to the side of the board.

(Turn 6 Environment Phase continues onto next page)

Finally, we will see how your assets and economy are doing.

1. Give players **10** new poker chips (🎰). They may keep any saved poker chips from the previous turn for their economy.
2. Count how many Economic Drivers (🌿) are on the map: _____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Economic Drivers on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Economic Drivers on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
3. Count how many Wildlife (🐦) are on the map: _____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Wildlife on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Wildlife on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
4. Count how many Aquatic Life (🐟) are on the map: _____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Aquatic Life on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Aquatic Life on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
5. Finally, resolve any Actions that may add or remove chips from the economy:
 - a. Some cards require persistent investment over each turn to keep them on the map. Let players choose whether they'd like to keep them or not.
 - b. Some cards add poker chips to the economy. Add these immediately.
 - c. Write the budget at the end of the Environment Phase, keeping track of debt: _____

Turn 7: Action Phase

Remove the top sticky note at the bottom of the board to reveal the year.

The year is **2090**. The Coastal Plain of North Carolina looks like this now. Our state has grown in population, and the coastline has shifted. The actions that you have invested in have benefited North Carolinians and the ecosystems they rely on.

It is up to you to continue to invest in actions that will benefit our Coastal Plain.

Your budget now is _____

Decide how many actions your players will have to choose from this turn: six (2 actions from each deck) or nine (3 actions from each deck). Fill in the blanks below based on your decision.

You and your team of statewide decision-makers must act quickly to protect the coastal plain of North Carolina and the people who live there. This turn, you may consider ___ different policy options available to you for investment.

- Turn over ___ cards available for play from the Resist Action Deck.
- Turn over ___ cards available for play from the Accept Action Deck.
- Turn over ___ cards available for play from the Direct Action Deck.

Each investment has a cost associated with it, which is marked on the card. You may invest in any of these actions as you choose, and you may invest in the same option more than once. Remember that to **invest in an action and to place an investment on the board**, your team must vote and have a majority in favor.

Read each action carefully, as they have different effects and consequences for the people and ecosystems on the coastline.

You may choose to spend none of your poker chips and save them. It is likely, but not guaranteed, that you will have saved poker chips carry over for the next turn.

You and your team have 10 minutes to make decisions about what actions are best for the coastal plain – starting now.

Begin the 10 minute timer for the Actions Phase.

Turn 7: Environment Phase

Let's see what happens between 2090 and 2100!

The road systems in North Carolina are deteriorating with more extreme heat and more flooding events. **Do you want to spend 2 chips to upkeep the road systems?** If not, your facilitator (me) will remove 4 hexes with roads on them.

Resolve this immediately. If removing roads, use a marker to cross them out on the board.

Next, we will choose three (3) climate and weather event cards.

- Draw one (1) card from the Climate and Weather Event deck.
- Resolve the event as described on the card. Keep note of Actions that players invested in that may protect hexes.
- **Shuffle the card back into the deck and then draw a new card.**
- Repeat this until you have drawn and resolved three (3) climate and weather events.
- *If you drew a hurricane, refer to the hurricane paths maps to select one at random.*

The population of North Carolina's coastal plain is growing! Let's add population to the map.

- You may decide where to add **three (3) Less Resilient Population** tokens to the map.
- If they are placed on hexes with no *Population* tokens, place a gray sticker on the hex to convert it to *Developed*.

North Carolina's environment is changing!

- Look at the attached map of Sea Level Rise. Select **5 hexes** from the **1 FT, 2 FT, or 3 FT** of sea level rise and convert them to water by placing a sticker in their center.
- Any *Population* tokens in a hex converted to *Water* must be moved elsewhere on the board.

Finally, we will see how your assets and economy are doing.

1. Give players **10** new poker chips (🎰). They may keep any saved poker chips from the previous turn for their economy.
2. Count how many Economic Drivers (🌿) are on the map: ____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Economic Drivers on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Economic Drivers on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
3. Count how many Wildlife (🐦) are on the map: ____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Wildlife on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Wildlife on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
4. Count how many Aquatic Life (🐟) are on the map: ____
 - a. If there are more than 10 Aquatic Life on the map, add 3 poker chips to the economy.
 - b. If there are fewer than 5 Aquatic Life on the map, remove 3 poker chips from the economy.
5. Finally, resolve any Actions that may add or remove chips from the economy:
 - a. Some cards require persistent investment over each turn to keep them on the map. Let players choose whether they'd like to keep them or not.
 - b. Some cards add poker chips to the economy. Add these immediately.
 - c. Write the budget at the end of the Environment Phase, keeping track of debt: _____

Player Cheat Sheet and Actions Catalog

Ground Rules Reminders:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Majority consensus is required to invest in an action and majority consensus is required to decide where on the board to place investments. The facilitator has the final say. 		
<p>Hex Carrying Capacity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each hex on the board has a carrying capacity of three (3) tokens. Stacked <i>Population</i> tokens are considered one asset. Roads or transportation infrastructure are counted as one asset. Note this rule does not apply to the <i>Elevate Transportation Infrastructure (R8) Site-Specific Intervention</i> token. 	<p>Population:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Population</i> tokens can only be placed on hexes that contain or border transportation infrastructure. If a hex is <i>unDeveloped</i>, <i>Population</i> tokens cannot be stacked (i.e., cannot stack bricks). If a hex is <i>Developed</i>, <i>Population</i> tokens can be stacked. New <i>Population</i> tokens cannot be added to a hex that is <i>Protected</i>. If 4 or more <i>Population</i> tokens are on a hex, it automatically converts to <i>Developed</i>. 	<p>Other Assets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Site-Specific Interventions</i> can be added to any hex, unless otherwise stated on an action card. When adding site specific interventions to the board, write the ID on the tag. <i>Aquatic Life</i> tokens can be added to <i>Wetland</i> or <i>Water</i> hexes only. <i>Economic Driver</i> tokens can be added to any hex. <i>Wildlife</i> tokens can be added to any non-<i>Water</i> hex.

Actions Catalog:

Resist Action Deck			
ID	Title	Narrative	Investment
R1	Restore Wetlands	<i>Enhances biodiversity, mitigates flooding, and sequesters carbon.</i>	1 chip
R2	Create a Climate Resilient Industries Grant Program	<i>Supports the creation of new, climate resilient industrial operations, stimulating the economy.</i>	2 chips
R3	Restore Islands Using Dredge Material	<i>Enhances coastal resilience, safeguarding ecosystems and economies against erosion and storm damage.</i>	3 chips
R4	Hardened Seawall	<i>Protects coastal communities and infrastructure from flooding but may harm ecosystems by altering coastal dynamics</i>	3 chips
R5	Beach renourishment	<i>Increases tourism and provides some resilience to future flooding and erosion, but has environmental tradeoffs.</i>	4 chips
R6	Structural Investments in Vulnerable Military Installations	<i>Make investments to bolster protections in existing military installations from coastal and climate hazards.</i>	4 chips
R7	Upgrade Drainage Infrastructure	<i>Enhances resilience against extreme weather events and flooding.</i>	4 chips
R8	Elevate Transportation Infrastructure	<i>Increases resilience to flooding and rising sea levels, but may disrupt local ecosystems.</i>	5 chips
R9	Harden Utility Infrastructure	<i>Improves resilience against climate-related disruptions, ensuring reliable energy supply and reducing emissions.</i>	5 chips
R10	Dredge River or Intracoastal Waterway	<i>Increases commercial activities, stimulating the economy.</i>	6 chips

Accept Action Deck			
A1	Increase Local Emergency Management Staff	<i>New government program allocates funds to hire and train local emergency management staff, enhancing disaster response and recovery.</i>	1 chip per Turn
A2	Receive Grant to Reuse/Redevelop Industrial or Commercial Sites	<i>You receive a Brownfields grant to reuse or redevelop industrial or commercial sites, stimulating the economy.</i>	0 chips
A3	Invest in Nature-based Approaches to Water Management	<i>Partner with industry to implement nature-based land and water management practices that decrease flooding impacts to the surrounding area.</i>	2 chips
A4	Buyout and Move Residents	<i>Enhances climate resilience but may disrupt communities and exacerbate inequalities.</i>	2 chips
A5	Implement Infrastructure Disinvestment Policy	<i>Policy strategically disinvests in infrastructure to prioritize resources elsewhere.</i>	0 chips
A6	Prohibit New Development in Floodplains	<i>A moratorium is placed on any new development in the 100- and 500-year floodplain.</i>	5 chips
A7	Implement a Transfer of Development Rights Program	<i>A market-based incentive directing development away from high-risk areas and/or sensitive agricultural or environmental resources ("sending area"), while incentivizing development in more desirable and/or less vulnerable areas ("receiving area").</i>	6 chips
A8	Acquire Land for Preservation	<i>Preserves habitat and connects landscape corridors to enable ecosystem migration.</i>	7 chips
A9	Relocate a Military Installation	<i>Secures defense, workforce, infrastructure, and populace in less vulnerable areas. Prior military land is now protected, creating ecotourism opportunities.</i>	8 chips
Direct Action Deck			
D1	Build New Land-based Renewable Energy Infrastructure	<i>Enhances redundancy of the energy grid to benefit coastal communities and economies, and reduces reliance on fossil fuels. Provides economic resiliency opportunities for agricultural operations.</i>	1 chip
D2	Build Offshore Wind	<i>Enhances redundancy of the energy grid to benefit coastal communities and economies, and reduces reliance on fossil fuels. Leads to decreases in local tourism due to perceived visual and environmental impacts.</i>	3 chips
D3	Build Living Shoreline	<i>Protects coastlines from flooding and storm damage while fostering biodiversity and ecosystem health.</i>	2 chips
D4	Make Resilience Retrofits to Existing Buildings	<i>Enhances climate resilience by fortifying structures against extreme weather events.</i>	3 chips
D5	Apply Firewise Concepts to Structures	<i>Enhances climate resilience by mitigating wildfire risks and protecting communities</i>	3 chips
D6	Convert Lands for Urban Development	<i>Improves climate resilience through efficient infrastructure, green spaces, and adaptive planning</i>	5 chips
D7	Transition to Climate-Smart Agriculture and Forest Practices	<i>Employ practices in agriculture, ranching, and forestry operations to adapt to the impacts of climate change and contribute to solutions that help to limit future climate change.</i>	6 chips
D8	Build High Speed Rail Infrastructure	<i>Spurs economic benefits with more efficient travel with reduced overall emissions and road congestion.</i>	7 chips
D9	Pass a Statewide Growth Management Policy	<i>Promotes compact urban development, mitigates new emissions, and preserves natural habitats.</i>	8 chips

FutureScape Note Taking Template

Participants will take notes during the game. Pass this around so that a different player is taking notes during each turn.

Table Name/ID	
Table Facilitator	
Group Members <i>(Name and Disciplinary Area Represented)</i>	

Turn: _____	Year: _____
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FutureScape Actions Cards Catalog

Resist Action Deck (10 cards)

R1 - Restore Wetlands – Cost: 1 chip

- **Narrative:** Enhances biodiversity, mitigates flooding, and sequesters carbon.
- **Placement:** Place a brown sticker on 1 *unDeveloped* hex to turn it into *Wetland*.
- **Effects:** Add 1 *Wildlife* or 1 *Aquatic Life* token to this hex.

R2 - Create a Climate Resilient Industries Grant Program – Cost: 2 chips

- **Narrative:** Supports the creation of new, climate resilient industrial operations, stimulating the economy.
- **Placement:** Place a sticker on 1 non-*Protected* hex to convert it to *Agriculture* (yellow sticker) or *Forest* (green sticker).
- **Effects:** Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to this hex, and 1 *Wildlife* token to a nearby hex.

R3 - Restore Islands Using Dredge Material – Cost: 3 chips

- **Narrative:** Enhances coastal resilience, safeguarding ecosystems and economies against erosion and storm damage.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *R3*, on a hex that borders *Water*.
- **Effects:** Add 1 *Wildlife* token to the hex and 1 *Aquatic Life* token to an adjacent *Water* or *Wetlands* hex.

R4 - Hardened Seawall – Cost: 3 chips

- **Narrative:** Protects coastal communities and infrastructure from flooding but may harm ecosystems by altering coastal dynamics.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *R4*, on a hex that borders *Water*.
- **Effects:** Remove all *Living Shoreline (D3) Site-Specific Interventions* from the hex. Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex. Lose all adjacent *Wildlife* and *Aquatic Life* tokens. Convert 1 adjacent *Wetland* hex to *Water* by placing a blue sticker in the center of the hex.

R5 - Beach renourishment – Cost: 4 chips

- **Narrative:** Increases tourism and provides some resilience to future flooding and erosion, but has environmental tradeoffs.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *R5*, on a hex that borders *Water*.
- **Effects:** Lose all adjacent *Aquatic Life*.

R6 - Structural Investments in Vulnerable Military Installations – Cost: 4 chips

- **Narrative:** Make investments to bolster protections in existing military installations from coastal and climate hazards.
- **Placement:** Select a *Military Installation* and place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *R6*, on it.
- **Effects:** Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to the hex. Convert 1 *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex or in a hex adjacent to it.

R7 - Upgrade Drainage Infrastructure – Cost: 4 chips

- **Narrative:** Enhances resilience against extreme weather events and flooding.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *R7*, on a hex with *Less Resilient Population*.
- **Effects:** Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex.

R8 - Elevate Transportation Infrastructure – Cost: 8 chips

- **Narrative:** Increases resilience to flooding and rising sea levels, but may disrupt local ecosystems.
- **Placement:** Choose a transportation corridor and place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *R8*, along its length. This intervention applies to the whole corridor. (This asset token does not count toward the hex's carrying capacity).

- **Effects:** In hexes that intersect this corridor: Convert 1 *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population*; lose 1 *Wildlife* or 1 *Aquatic Life* token.

R9 - Harden Utility Infrastructure – Cost: 5 chips

- **Narrative:** Improves resilience against climate-related disruptions, ensuring reliable energy supply and reducing emissions.
- **Placement:** Place 2 *Site-Specific Interventions*, labeled R9, on 2 hexes. The hexes do not need to be adjacent to one another.
- **Effects:** Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in these hexes.

R10 - Dredge River or Intracoastal Waterway – Cost: 6 chips

- **Narrative:** Increases commercial activities, stimulating the economy.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled R10, in any *Water* hex bordered by land.
- **Effects:** Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to an adjacent hex. Lose all adjacent *Aquatic Life*.

Accept Action Deck (9 cards)

A1 - Increase Local Emergency Management Staff – Cost: 1 chip per turn.

- **Narrative:** New government program allocates funds to hire and train local emergency management staff, enhancing disaster response and recovery.
- **Placement:** Board-wide policy. Place this card in the *Board-wide Policy* board area.
- **Effects:** Total penalty for any event from the Climate and Weather Events Deck is reduced by 1 chip.
- **Retain this Effect:** Pay 1 chip during the Environment’s Phase to keep this policy.

A2 - Receive Grant to Reuse/Redevelop Industrial or Commercial Sites – Cost: 0 chips

- **Narrative:** You receive a Brownfields grant to reuse or redevelop industrial or commercial sites, stimulating the economy.
- **Placement:** Board-wide policy. May only be played once per turn.
- **Effects:** Immediately gain 2 chips.

A3 - Invest in Nature-based Approaches to Water Management – Cost: 2 chips

- **Narrative:** Partner with industry to implement nature-based land and water management practices that decrease flooding impacts to the surrounding area.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled A3, on an *unDeveloped* hex.
- **Effects:** Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to an adjacent hex.

A4 - Buyout and Move Residents – Cost: 2 chips

- **Narrative:** Enhances climate resilience but may disrupt communities and exacerbate inequalities.
- **Placement:** Relocate 1-2 *Population* tokens from one hex to another.
- **Effects:** Convert relocated *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population*.

A5 - Implement Infrastructure Disinvestment Policy – Cost: 0 chips

- **Narrative:** Policy strategically disinvests in infrastructure to prioritize resources elsewhere.
- **Placement:** Select a hex and remove all *Site-Specific Interventions* and investments. This includes pre-game investments, such as highways and bridges (use a marker cross out investments as needed).
- **Effects:** Immediately gain 2 chips.

A6 - Prohibit New Development in Floodplains – Cost: 5 chips

- **Narrative:** A moratorium is placed on any new development in the 100- and 500-year floodplain.
- **Placement:** Board-wide policy. Place this card in the Board-wide Policy board area.
- **Effects:** As long as this moratorium is in effect, all new *Population* placed on the board is *More Resilient Population*.
- **Remove this effect:** The moratorium may be lifted by paying 5 chips.

A7 - Implement a Transfer of Development Rights Program – Cost: 6 chips

- **Narrative:** A market-based incentive directing development away from high-risk areas and/or sensitive agricultural or environmental resources ("sending area"), while incentivizing development in more desirable and/or less vulnerable areas ("receiving area").
- **Placement:** Choose 1 *Forest*, *Agriculture*, or *Wetland* hex to protect (draw hashed lines), and 1 to convert to *Developed* (place gray sticker).
- **Effects:** Add 1 *Economic Driver*, *Wildlife*, or *Aquatic Life* token to the area of the newly protected hex.

A8 - Acquire Land for Preservation – Cost: 7 chips

- **Narrative:** Preserves habitat and connects landscape corridors to enable ecosystem migration.
- **Placement:** Choose 1 *Agriculture*, *Forest*, or *Wetland* hex with no *Population* tokens and convert it to *Protected* (draw hashed lines).
- **Effects:** Add 1 *Wildlife* token and 1 *Aquatic Life* token to the area.

A9 - Relocate a Military Installation – Cost: 8 chips

- **Narrative:** Secures defense, workforce, infrastructure, and populace in less vulnerable areas. Prior military land is now protected, creating ecotourism opportunities.
- **Placement:** Move a *Military Installation* to a less vulnerable area. Move up to two *Population* tokens near the original location to an adjacent hex of the new location. This action may apply to *Military Installations* in the *Lost Resources* area, in which case you cannot move it back to its original location.
- **Effects:** Add 2 *Wildlife* tokens and 1 *Aquatic Life* token to the original *Military Installation* hex or any of its adjacent hexes. Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to the new *Military Installation* hex or one of its neighbors.

Direct Action Deck (9 cards)

D1 - Build New Land-based Renewable Energy Infrastructure - Cost: 1 chip

- **Narrative:** Enhances redundancy of the energy grid to benefit coastal communities and economies, and reduces reliance on fossil fuels. Provides economic resiliency opportunities for agricultural operations.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *D1*, to an *Agriculture* or *Developed* hex.
- **Effects:** Lose 1 *Wildlife* token from the hex or one of its neighbors.

D2 - Build Offshore Wind – Cost: 3 chips

- **Narrative:** Enhances redundancy of the energy grid to benefit coastal communities and economies, and reduces reliance on fossil fuels. Decreases local tourism due to perceived visual and environmental impacts.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *D2*, to a *Water* hex.
- **Effects:** Lose 1 *Wildlife* or 1 *Aquatic Life* token from the hex or one of its neighbors.

D3 - Build Living Shoreline – Cost: 2 chips

- **Narrative:** Protects coastlines from flooding and storm damage while fostering biodiversity and ecosystem health.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *D3*, in a hex that borders *Water*.
- **Effects:** Remove all *Hardened Seawall (R4) Site-Specific Interventions* from the hex. Add (total) 1 *Wildlife* token and 1 *Aquatic Life* token to nearby hexes.

D4 - Make Resilience Retrofits to Existing Buildings – Cost: 3 chips

- **Narrative:** Enhances climate resilience by fortifying structures against extreme weather events.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *D4*, in a hex containing *Population* token(s).
- **Effects:** Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex.

D5 - Apply Firewise Concepts to Structures – Cost: 3 chips

- **Narrative:** Enhances climate resilience by mitigating wildfire risks and protecting communities.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *D5*, in a hex.
- **Effects:** Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex.

D6 - Convert Lands for Urban Development – Cost: 5 chips

- **Narrative:** Improves climate resilience through efficient infrastructure, green spaces, and adaptive planning.
- **Placement:** Choose a non-*Protected* hex that contains transportation infrastructure or that is adjacent to a hex with transportation infrastructure. Place a gray sticker to convert the hex to *Developed*.
- **Effects:** Lose all *Wildlife* and *Aquatic Life* tokens in the hex. Lose 1 additional *Wildlife* token from an adjacent hex.

D7 - Transition to Climate-Smart Agriculture and Forest Practices – Cost: 6 chips

- **Narrative:** Employ practices in agriculture, ranching, and forestry operations to adapt to the impacts of climate change and contribute to solutions that help to limit future climate change.
- **Placement:** Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *D7*, in an *unDeveloped* hex.
- **Effects:** Add 1 *Economic Driver token*, 1 *Wildlife token*, and 1 *Aquatic Life token* to the hex or any of its neighbors.

D8 - Build High Speed Rail Infrastructure – Cost: 7 chips

- **Narrative:** Spurs economic benefits with more efficient travel with reduced overall emissions and road congestion.
- **Placement:** Draw any length line between two hexes of your choosing.
- **Effects:** Lose 1 *Wildlife token* and 1 *Aquatic Life token* from any hex in the new rail path.

D9 - Pass a Statewide Growth Management Policy – Cost: 6 chips

- **Narrative:** Promotes compact urban development, mitigates new emissions, and preserves natural habitats.
- **Placement:** Board-wide policy. Place this card in the *Board-wide Policy* board area.
- **Effects:** *Population* tokens can now stack on any non-*Water* hex, regardless of development. Once this action is played, any hex that is converted to *Developed* must be adjacent to an existing *Developed* hex.
- **Clarifying note:** This action restricts development by the 4+ *Population* token ground rule and impacts where new *Population* tokens are placed during the *Environment* phase. It also increases the carrying capacity of *unDeveloped* hexes (see carrying capacity rule).
- **Remove this effect:** The policy may be removed by paying 8 chips.

FutureScape Weather and Climate Events Cards Catalog

Normal

- **Location:** Board-wide.
- **Effects:** No event to resolve.

Deep Freeze

- **Location:** Facilitator picks one *Agriculture* hex on the board. The impacted area extends over 3 concentric rows of hexes.
- **Effects:** Lose half of affected *Economic Driver* tokens (move them to the *Lost Resources* board area).

Wildfire

- **Location:** Facilitator picks one *Forest* hex on the board.
- **Protections:** Any hex containing or bordering *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *D5 (Apply Firewise Concepts)* or *D7 (Climate-Smart Agriculture and Forestry)* is protected from damage. Remove these *Site-Specific Interventions* from the board before the next turn.
- **Effects:** Lose all affected *Economic Driver* and *Wildlife* tokens. Convert any impacted *More Resilient Population* to *Less Resilient Population*.

Harmful Algal Bloom

- **Location:** Facilitator picks 1 *Water* hex bordering land.
- **Protections:** Any hex containing or bordering *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *A3 (Nature Based Solution)* or *D3 (Living Shoreline)* is protected from damage.
- **Effects:** In the hex and all its neighbors: Lose all affected *Wildlife* and *Aquatic Life* tokens. Lose 1 chip from the budget.

Drought

- **Location:** Facilitator picks 1 hex on the board. The impacted area extends over 3 concentric rows of hexes.
- **Protections:** Any hex containing or bordering *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *A3 (Nature Based Solution)* is protected from damage.
- **Effects:** Lose half of all affected *Economic Driver*, *Wildlife*, and *Aquatic Life* tokens. Lose 1 chip for the budget.

Super Drought

- **Location:** Board-wide impact.
- **Protections:** Any hex containing a *Site-Specific Intervention* labeled *A3 (Nature Based Solution)* is protected from damage.
- **Effects:** Lose 2 *Economic Driver*, 2 *Wildlife*, and 2 *Aquatic Life* tokens. Lose 4 chips from the budget.

Extreme Heat + Rolling Blackouts

- **Location:** Board-wide impact.
- **Protections:** If 2 or more *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *D1* or *D2 (Renewable Energy Infrastructure)* are on the board, no damage is experienced.
- **Effects:** Lose 1 *Economic Driver*, 1 *Wildlife*, and 1 *Aquatic Life* tokens from the board. Convert 2 *More Resilient Population* tokens, 1 of which is on a *Developed* hex, to *Less Resilient Population*.

Non-Hurricane Rain-Induced Flooding Event

- **Location:** Facilitator picks 2 adjacent hexes.
- **Protections:** Any transportation routes with *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *R8 (Elevate Infrastructure)* are protected from damage. Any hexes with *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *R7 (Upgrade Drainage Infrastructure)* are protected from damage.
- **Effects:** Lose 1 chip for every *Population* token, *Site-Specific Intervention*, or transportation segment impacted.

Unanticipated Coastal Inundation

- **Location:** Facilitator picks 1 hex bordering Water.
- **Protections:** If the hex contains a *Site-Specific Intervention* (excluding D5 or D8), the hex is protected from damage.
- **Effects:** Convert 1 *More Resilient Population* to *Less Resilient Population* in the impacted hex. Lose 1 Wildlife token from the impacted hex.

Category 1 Hurricane:

- **Location:** Facilitator picks a 1-hex wide path following the image.
- **Protections:** If the *Prohibit New Development in Floodplains* (A6) policy is in play, displaced populations may relocate anywhere. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* (excluding D5), is protected from damage.
- **Effects:** One (1) impacted *Less Resilient Population* must relocate to a nearby location (1 to 2 hexes away).

Category 2 Hurricane:

- **Location:** Facilitator picks a 2-hex wide path following the image.
- **Protections:** If the *Prohibit New Development in Floodplains* (A6) policy is in play, displaced populations may relocate anywhere. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* (excluding D5), is protected from damage.
- **Effects:** Three (3) impacted *Less Resilient Population* must relocate to nearby locations (1 to 2 hexes away). Two (2) of the impacted *More Resilient Population* are converted to *Less Resilient*. Lose 1 Wildlife token.

Category 3 Hurricane:

- **Location:** Facilitator picks a 3-hex wide path following the image.
- **Protections:** If the *Prohibit New Development in Floodplains* (A6) policy is in play, displaced populations may relocate anywhere. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled R3-R7 is protected from damage; remove these tokens from the board after resolving this event. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled R8-R9, A3, D1-D8 (excluding D5), is protected.
- **Effects:** Three (3) impacted *More Resilient Population* converts to *Less Resilient Population*. Three (3) of the impacted *Population* tokens must relocate to nearby locations (2 to 4 hexes away). Lose 2 tokens (each) of *Wildlife*, *Aquatic Life*, and *Economic Drivers* from the storm's path.

Category 4 Hurricane:

- **Location:** Facilitator randomly picks a 4-hex wide path following the image.
- **Protections:** Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled R3-R7 is protected from damage; remove these tokens from the board after resolving this event. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled R8-R9, A3, D1-D8 (excluding D5), is protected.
- **Effects:** All impacted *More Resilient Population* tokens convert to *Less Resilient Population*. Four (4) of the impacted *Population* tokens must relocate to another *Developed* area. Lose 3 tokens (each) of *Wildlife*, *Aquatic Life*, and *Economic Drivers* from the storm's path.

Category 5 Hurricane:

- **Location:** Facilitator randomly picks a 5-hex wide path following the image.
- **Protections:** Any road segments with *Elevate Transportation Infrastructure* (R8), are protected from damage.
- **Effects:** Remove 1 *Population* token from the board. Four (4) *More Resilient Population* tokens are converted to *Less Resilient Population*. Five (5) of the impacted *Population* must relocate to another *Developed* area. Lose 1 chip for every *Site-Specific Intervention* in the storm's path. Lose 4 tokens (each) of *Wildlife*, *Aquatic Life*, and *Economic Drivers* from the storm's path. For any *Military Installations* in the storm's path, move all *Population* tokens within 1 hex to a *Military Installation* outside of the storm's path (within 1 hex of the new *Military Installation*).

Category 6 Hurricane:

- **Location:** Board-wide impacts.
- **Protections:** If the *Prohibit New Development in Floodplains (A6)* policy is in play, displaced populations may relocate anywhere.
- **Effects:** Remove 2 *Population* tokens from the board. Five (5) of *More Resilient Population* tokens are converted to *Less Resilient Population*. Facilitator selects 4 population tokens (from anywhere) and players relocate them. Lose 5 chips from the budget. Lose 5 tokens (each) of *Wildlife, Aquatic Life, and Economic Drivers*. Identify one *Military Installation* in a more vulnerable area and move all *Population* tokens and economic drivers within 1 hex to a *Military Installation* in a less vulnerable area (within 1 hex of the new *Military Installation*). Remove the affected *Military Installation* from the board.

FutureScape Actions Cards Print Template

Each card is labeled with the action type (“R” for “Resist”, “A” for “Accept” and “D” for “Direct”) as well as the action number (1-10) in the upper left.

(Card templates have been formatted to print double-sided, flipping on short edge)

R1

Restore Wetlands

Cost: 1 chip

Placement: Place a brown sticker on 1 *unDeveloped* hex to turn it into *Wetland*.

Effects: Add 1 *Wildlife* or 1 *Aquatic Life* token to this hex.

R2

Create a Climate Resilient Industries Grant Program

Cost: 2 chips

Placement: Place a sticker on 1 non-*Protected* hex to convert it to *Agriculture* (yellow sticker) or *Forest* (green sticker).

Effects: Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to this hex, and 1 *Wildlife* token to a nearby hex.

R3

Restore Islands Using Dredge Material

Cost: 3 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled R3, on a hex that borders *Water*.

Effects: Add 1 *Wildlife* token to the hex and 1 *Aquatic Life* token to an adjacent *Water* or *Wetlands* hex.

R4

Hardened Seawall

Cost: 3 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled R4, on a hex that borders *Water*.

Effects: Remove all *Living Shoreline (D3) Site-Specific Interventions* from the hex. Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex. Lose all adjacent *Wildlife* and *Aquatic Life* tokens. Convert 1 adjacent *Wetland* hex to *Water* by placing a blue sticker in the center of the hex.

Resist

Resist

Resist

Resist

R5

Beach Renourishment

Cost: 4 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled R5, on a hex that borders *Water*.

Effects: Lose all adjacent *Aquatic Life*.

R6

Structural Investments in Vulnerable Military Installations

Cost: 4 chips

Placement: Select a *Military Installation* and place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled R6, on it.

Effects: Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to the hex. Convert 1 *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex or in a hex adjacent to it.

R7

Upgrade Drainage Infrastructure

Cost: 4 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled R7, on a hex with *Less Resilient Population*.

Effects: Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex.

R8

Elevate Transportation Infrastructure

Cost: 8 chips

Placement: Choose a transportation corridor and place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled R8, along its length. This intervention applies to the whole corridor. (This asset token does not count toward the hex's carrying capacity).

Effects: In hexes that intersect this corridor: Convert 1 *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population*; lose 1 *Wildlife* or 1 *Aquatic Life* token.

Resist

Resist

Resist

Resist

R9

Harden Utility Infrastructure

Cost: 5 chips

Placement: Place 2 *Site-Specific Interventions*, labeled R9, on 2 hexes. The hexes do not need to be adjacent to one another.

Effects: Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in these hexes.

R10

Dredge River or Intracoastal Waterway

Cost: 6 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled R10, in any *Water* hex bordered by land.

Effects: Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to an adjacent hex. Lose all adjacent *Aquatic Life*.

A1

Increase Local Emergency Management Staff

Cost: 1 chip per Turn

Placement: Board-wide policy. Place this card in the *Board-wide Policy* board area.

Effects: Total penalty for any event from the Climate and Weather Events Deck is reduced by 1 chip

Retain this Effect: Pay 1 chip during the Environment's Phase to keep this policy.

A2

Receive Grant to Reuse/Redevelop Industrial or Commercial Sites

Cost: 0 chips

Placement: Board-wide policy. May only be played once per turn.

Effects: Immediately gain 2 chips.

Resist

Resist

Accept

Accept

A3

Invest in Nature-based Approaches to Water Management

Cost: 2 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled A3, on an *unDeveloped* hex.

Effects: Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to an adjacent hex.

A4

Buyout and Move Residents

Cost: 2 chips

Placement: Relocate 1-2 *Population* tokens from one hex to another.

Effects: Convert relocated *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population*.

A5

Implement Infrastructure Disinvestment Policy

Cost: 0 chips

Placement: Select a hex and remove all *Site-Specific Interventions* and investments. This includes pre-game investments, such as highways and bridges (use a marker cross out investments as needed).

Effects: Immediately gain 2 chips.

A6

Prohibit New Development in Floodplains

Cost: 5 chips

Placement: Board-wide policy. Place this card in the Board-wide Policy board area.

Effects: As long as this moratorium is in effect, all new *Population* placed on the board is *More Resilient Population*.

Remove this effect: The moratorium may be lifted by paying 5 chips.

Accept

Accept

Accept

Accept

A7

Implement a Transfer of Development Rights Program

Cost: 6 chips

Placement: Choose 1 *Forest*, *Agriculture*, or *Wetland* hex to protect (draw hashed lines), and 1 to convert to *Developed* (place gray sticker).

Effects: Add 1 *Economic Driver*, *Wildlife*, or *Aquatic Life* token to the area of the newly protected hex.

A8

Acquire Land for Preservation

Cost: 7 chips

Placement: Choose 1 *Agriculture*, *Forest*, or *Wetland* hex with no *Population* tokens and convert it to *Protected* (draw hashed lines).

Effects: Add 1 *Wildlife* token and 1 *Aquatic Life* token to the area.

A9

Relocate a Military Installation

Cost: 8 chips

Placement: Move a *Military Installation* to a less vulnerable area. Move up to two *Population* tokens near the original location to an adjacent hex of the new location. This action may apply to *Military Installations* in the *Lost Resources* area, in which case you cannot move it back to its original location.

Effects: Add 2 *Wildlife* tokens and 1 *Aquatic Life* token to the original *Military Installation* hex or any of its adjacent hexes. Add 1 *Economic Driver* token to the new *Military Installation* hex or one of its neighbors.

D1

Build New Land-based Renewable Energy Infrastructure

Cost: 1 chip

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *D1*, to an *Agriculture* or *Developed* hex.

Effects: Lose 1 *Wildlife* token from the hex or one of its neighbors.

Accept

Accept

Direct

Accept

D2

Build Offshore Wind

Cost: 3 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled D2, to a *Water* hex.

Effects: Lose 1 *Wildlife* or 1 *Aquatic Life* token from the hex or one of its neighbors.

D3

Build Living Shoreline

Cost: 2 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled D3, in a hex that borders *Water*.

Effects: Remove all *Hardened Seawall (R4) Site-Specific Interventions* from the hex. Add (total) 1 *Wildlife* token and 1 *Aquatic Life* token to nearby hexes.

D4

Make Resilience Retrofits to Existing Buildings

Cost: 3 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled D4, in a hex containing *Population* token(s).

Effects: Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex.

D5

Apply Firewise Concepts to Structures

Cost: 3 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled D5, in a hex.

Effects: Convert all *Less Resilient Population* to *More Resilient Population* in the hex.

Direct

Direct

Direct

Direct

D6

Convert Lands for Urban Development

Cost: 5 chips

Placement: Choose a non-*Protected* hex that contains transportation infrastructure or that is adjacent to a hex with transportation infrastructure. Place a gray sticker to convert the hex to *Developed*.

Effects: Lose all *Wildlife* and *Aquatic Life* tokens in the hex. Lose 1 additional *Wildlife* token from an adjacent hex.

D7

Transition to Climate-Smart Agriculture and Forest Practices

Cost: 6 chips

Placement: Place 1 *Site-Specific Intervention*, labeled *D7*, in an *unDeveloped* hex.

Effects: Add 1 *Economic Driver* token, 1 *Wildlife* token, and 1 *Aquatic Life* token to the hex or any of its neighbors.

D8

Build High Speed Rail Infrastructure

Cost: 7 chips

Placement: Draw any length line between two hexes of your choosing.

Effects: Lose 1 *Wildlife* token and 1 *Aquatic Life* token from any hex in the new rail path.

D9

Pass a Statewide Growth Management Policy

Cost: 6 chips

Placement: Board-wide policy. Place this card in the *Board-wide Policy* board area.

Effects: *Population* tokens can now stack on any non-*Water* hex, regardless of development. Once this action is played, any hex that is converted to *Developed* must be adjacent to an existing *Developed* hex.

Remove this effect: The policy may be removed by paying 8 chips.

Direct

Direct

Direct

Direct

***FutureScape* Climate and Weather Events Card Deck Print Template**

(Card templates have been formatted to print double-sided, flipping on short edge)

Normal

Location: Board-wide.

Effects: No event to resolve.

Normal

Location: Board-wide.

Effects: No event to resolve.

Normal

Location: Board-wide.

Effects: No event to resolve.

Normal

Location: Board-wide.

Effects: No event to resolve.

**Climate & Weather
Events Deck**

Normal

Location: Board-wide.

Effects: No event to resolve.

Normal

Location: Board-wide.

Effects: No event to resolve.

Deep Freeze

Location: Facilitator picks one *Agriculture* hex on the board. The impacted area extends over 3 concentric rows of hexes.

Effects: Lose half of affected *Economic Driver* tokens (move them to the *Lost Resources* board area).

Wildfire

Location: Facilitator picks one *Forest* hex on the board.

Protections: Any hex containing or bordering *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *D5 (Apply Firewise Concepts)* or *D7 (Climate-Smart Agriculture and Forestry)* is protected from damage. Remove these *Site-Specific Interventions* from the board before the next turn.

Effects: Lose all affected *Economic Driver* and *Wildlife* tokens. Convert any impacted *More Resilient Population* to *Less Resilient Population*.

**Climate & Weather
Events Deck**

Harmful Algal Bloom

Location: Facilitator picks 1 *Water* hex bordering land.

Protections: Any hex containing or bordering *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *A3 (Nature Based Solution)* or *D3 (Living Shoreline)* is protected from damage.

Effects: In the hex and all its neighbors: Lose all affected *Wildlife* and *Aquatic Life* tokens. Lose 1 chip from the budget.

Drought

Location: Facilitator picks 1 hex on the board. The impacted area extends over 3 concentric rows of hexes.

Protections: Any hex containing or bordering *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *A3 (Nature Based Solution)* is protected from damage.

Effects: Lose half of all affected *Economic Driver*, *Wildlife*, and *Aquatic Life* tokens. Lose 1 chip for the budget.

Drought

Location: Facilitator picks 1 hex on the board. The impacted area extends over 3 concentric rows of hexes.

Protections: Any hex containing or bordering *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *A3 (Nature Based Solution)* is protected from damage.

Effects: Lose half of all affected *Economic Driver*, *Wildlife*, and *Aquatic Life* tokens. Lose 1 chip for the budget.

Super Drought

Location: Board-wide impact.

Protections: Any hex containing a *Site-Specific Intervention* labeled *A3 (Nature Based Solution)* is protected from damage.

Effects: Lose 2 *Economic Driver*, 2 *Wildlife*, and 2 *Aquatic Life* tokens. Lose 4 chips from the budget.

**Climate & Weather
Events Deck**

Extreme Heat + Rolling Blackouts

Location: Board-wide impact.

Protections: If 2 or more *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *D1* or *D2* (*Renewable Energy Infrastructure*) are on the board, no damage is experienced.

Effects: Lose 1 *Economic Driver*, 1 *Wildlife*, and 1 *Aquatic Life* tokens from the board. Convert 2 *More Resilient Population* tokens, 1 of which is on a *Developed* hex, to *Less Resilient Population*.

Non-Hurricane Rain-Induced Flooding Event

Location: Facilitator picks 2 adjacent hexes.

Protections: Any transportation routes with *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *R8* (*Elevate Infrastructure*) are protected from damage. Any hexes with *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled *R7* (*Upgrade Drainage Infrastructure*) are protected from damage.

Effects: Lose 1 chip for every *Population* token, *Site-Specific Intervention*, or transportation segment impacted.

Unanticipated Coastal Inundation

Location: Facilitator picks 1 hex bordering *Water*.

Protections: If the hex contains a *Site-Specific Intervention* (excluding *D5* or *D8*), the hex is protected from damage.

Effects: Convert 1 *More Resilient Population* to *Less Resilient Population* in the impacted hex. Lose 1 *Wildlife* token from the impacted hex.

Unanticipated Coastal Inundation

Location: Facilitator picks 1 hex bordering *Water*.

Protections: If the hex contains a *Site-Specific Intervention* (excluding *D5* or *D8*), the hex is protected from damage.

Effects: Convert 1 *More Resilient Population* to *Less Resilient Population* in the impacted hex. Lose 1 *Wildlife* token from the impacted hex.

**Climate & Weather
Events Deck**

Unanticipated Coastal Inundation

Location: Facilitator picks 1 hex bordering *Water*.

Protections: If the hex contains a *Site-Specific Intervention (excluding D5 or D8)*, the hex is protected from damage.

Effects: Convert 1 *More Resilient Population* to *Less Resilient Population* in the impacted hex. Lose 1 *Wildlife* token from the impacted hex.

Category 1 Hurricane

Location: Facilitator picks a 1-hex wide path following the image.

Protections: If the *Prohibit New Development in Floodplains (A6)* policy is in play, displaced populations may relocate anywhere. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions (excluding D5)*, is protected from damage.

Effects: One (1) impacted *Less Resilient Population* must relocate to a nearby location (1 to 2 hexes away).

Category 2 Hurricane

Location: Facilitator picks a 2-hex wide path following the image.

Protections: If the *Prohibit New Development in Floodplains (A6)* policy is in play, displaced populations may relocate anywhere. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions (excluding D5)*, is protected from damage.

Effects: Three (3) impacted *Less Resilient Population* must relocate to nearby locations (1 to 2 hexes away). Two (2) of the impacted *More Resilient Population* are converted to *Less Resilient*. Lose 1 *Wildlife* token.

Category 3 Hurricane

Location: Facilitator picks a 3-hex wide path following the image.

Protections: If the *Prohibit New Development in Floodplains (A6)* policy is in play, displaced populations may relocate anywhere. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled R3-R7 is protected from damage; remove these tokens from the board after resolving this event. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled R8-R9, A3, D1-D8 (*excluding D5*), is protected.

Effects: Three (3) impacted *More Resilient Population* converts to *Less Resilient Population*. Three (3) of the impacted *Population* tokens must relocate to nearby locations (2 to 4 hexes away). Lose 2 tokens (each) of *Wildlife*, *Aquatic Life*, and *Economic Drivers* from the storm's path.

**Climate & Weather
Events Deck**

Category 4 Hurricane

Location: Facilitator randomly picks a 4-hex wide path following the image.

Protections: Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled R3-R7 is protected from damage; remove these tokens from the board after resolving this event. Any hex containing *Site-Specific Interventions* labeled R8-R9, A3, D1-D8 (*excluding D5*), is protected.

Effects: All impacted *More Resilient Population* tokens convert to *Less Resilient Population*. Four (4) of the impacted *Population* tokens must relocate to another *Developed* area. Lose 3 tokens (each) of *Wildlife*, *Aquatic Life*, and *Economic Drivers* from the storm's path.

Category 5 Hurricane

Location: Facilitator randomly picks a 4-hex wide path following the image.

Protections: Any road segments with *Elevate Transportation Infrastructure* (R8), are protected from damage.

Effects: Remove 1 *Population* token from the board. Four (4) *More Resilient Population* tokens are converted to *Less Resilient Population*. Five (5) of the impacted *Population* must relocate to another *Developed* area. Lose 1 chip for every *Site-Specific Intervention* in the storm's path. Lose 4 tokens (each) of *Wildlife*, *Aquatic Life*, and *Economic Drivers* from the storm's path. For any *Military Installations* in the storm's path, move all *Population* tokens within 1 hex to a *Military Installation* outside of the storm's path (within 1 hex of the new *Military Installation*).

Category 6 Hurricane

Location: Board-wide impacts.

Protections: If the *Prohibit New Development in Floodplains* (A6) policy is in play, displaced populations may relocate anywhere.

Effects: Remove 2 *Population* tokens from the board. Five (5) of *More Resilient Population* tokens are converted to *Less Resilient Population*. Facilitator selects 4 population tokens (from anywhere) and players relocate them. Lose 5 chips from the budget. Lose 5 tokens (each) of *Wildlife*, *Aquatic Life*, and *Economic Drivers*. Identify one *Military Installation* in a more vulnerable area and move all *Population* tokens and economic drivers within 1 hex to a *Military Installation* in a less vulnerable area (within 1 hex of the new *Military Installation*). Remove the affected *Military Installation* from the board.

***FutureScape* Hurricane Track Cards**

If a hurricane event card is drawn during the Environment Phase, randomly draw one of the Hurricane Track cards to determine the storm's path.

Facilitator's Choice (choose your own hurricane path)

Hurricane Path Deck

Hurricane Path Deck

Hurricane Path Deck

Hurricane Path Deck

FutureScape Sea Level Rise Key

- 1 ft Sea Level Rise
- 2 ft Sea Level Rise
- 3 ft Sea Level Rise

